

Review on the Progress in the Role of Herbal Feeds in Freshwater Aquaculture

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Abstract

Fish of commercial importance are farmed in captivity under controlled conditions to fulfill the demand of white meat for human consumption. Hence, increased intensification of aquaculture has led to many constraints including, poor growth, and poor health. This has made it hard for fish farmers to turn the biological benefits associated with intensive farming systems into economical gain. Moreover, the wide adoption use of chemotherapeutic drugs to maintain health and hormones to control reproduction appears to be merely production-oriented, thus unsustainable. Hence, improvement of productions in aquaculture should also focus on environmentally friendly and with sustainable methods. Today, huge attention is focused on the use of medicinal herbal extracts to improve yield in aquaculture as alternatives to chemical agents. Accordingly, the aim of this work was to critically review the effectiveness of herbal extracts in tilapia farming, and further highlight gaps in the existing knowledge and the way forward in using medicinal herbal extracts in tilapia aquaculture. A wide range of medicinal herbal products were reported to enhance growth, appetite, immune responses, antioxidation, hepatoprotective activity and control reproduction in fresh water fishes; attributed by their abundant bioactive phytochemicals. However, the lack of sufficient knowledge on herbs limits the cost-effective use of herbal extracts in freshwater fish culture. Modest knowledge still exists on application of herbs and their potential impacts on fish. More research is therefore deemed necessary to optimize the use of herbs in freshwater fish culture.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, aquaculture remains one of the fast growing food-producing sectors, with the highest potential to assist capture fisheries meet global demand for aquatic food (FAO, 2016). An impressive global production performance by aquaculture is a result of wide adoption of intensive production systems, which are associated with higher productivity per unit area as a result of higher stocking density (Basha *et al.*, 2013; Waite *et al.*, 2014). However, higher stocking density in intensive farming systems coupled with other general aquaculture activities such as fish handling,

transportation and harvesting may be stressful to fish. This may consequently lead to a number of conditions including poor metabolism capacity (Santos *et al.*, 2010), poor meat quality (Jittinandana *et al.*, 2003), increased susceptibility to diseases (Wu *et al.*, 2013) and in extreme cases lead to deaths (Mckenzie *et al.*, 2012). All these constraints have made it hard for fish farmers to convert the benefits of higher production yield associated with intensive production systems into economical gains. Thus, aquaculture is yet to reach its maximum potential.

In an effort for fish farmers to economically benefit from intensive farming systems, they started using synthetic antibiotics and other chemotherapeutic drugs to maintain good health of farmed fish. The adoption of these drugs in aquaculture appears to be only profit-driven and unsustainable, as they cause several other constraints such as fish pathogen drug resistance, immunosuppression, environmental pollution and accumulation of chemical residues, which can be potentially hazardous to the public health (Bulfinch *et al.*, 2013; WHO, 2006). Thus, many nations across the globe such as the United States, European Union (Bulfinch *et al.*, 2013), and Asian countries (Ji *et al.*, 2007) have strict demand for aquatic products free from chemical-drugs. Today, the need of replacing antibiotics and other synthetic chemicals with dietary supplements or ingredients that is capable of strengthening fish health, and enhance their growth, feed utilization ability, and ultimately ensure safety and good quality products from aquaculture are becoming increasingly vital.

Over the past two decades, there has been an increase in the number of research with common conclusions that indeed medicinal herbal extracts have the potential to eradicate the use of synthetic chemicals such as antibiotics and other chemotherapeutic drugs in aquaculture. Medicinal herbal extracts stand out as potential alternatives to synthetic drugs in aquaculture as they provide useful biologically active metabolites with various benefits such as immune modulating (Zanuzzo *et al.*, 2015; Yang *et al.*, 2015; Yilmaz and Ergün, 2018; Yilmaz, 2019a, 2019b), growth promoting, antioxidant enhancing, antidepressant, digestive enhancing, appetite-stimulating effects (Zhang *et al.*, 2010; Mahdavi *et al.*, 2013; Gabriel *et al.* 2015), and hepatoprotective effects (Gurkan *et al.*, 2015; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2014), if properly administered. Other reasons are that medicinal herbal extracts are easily available, inexpensive, and tend to be more biodegradable in nature compared to synthetic drugs (Olusola *et al.*, 2013; Reverter *et al.*, 2014).

Therefore the present review aims to highlight the effectiveness of few herbs and herbal supplementation in fish feed as growth promoters, appetizers, antioxidant, antidepressants with immunostimulant effects on farmed fish species. Present study further discussed gaps in the existing knowledge and the way forward in using medicinal herbal extracts as their use can be a sustainable and feasible strategy for the success of for freshwater fish culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is a review on the progress in the role of herbal feeds in freshwater aquaculture. It has been compiled primarily from articles and technical reports published in scientific journals. The related information has been compiled from literature published until December 2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Some medicinal herbs investigated

Citarasu *et al.*, (2001) controlled the pathogenic bacteria using herbal biomedical products in the larva culture system of *Penaeus monodon*. Omoregie (2001) studied the utilization and nutrient digestibility of mango seeds *Mangifera indica* and palm Kernel *Elaeis guineensis* meal by juvenile *Labeo senegalensis*. Citarasu *et al.*, (2002) developed the *Artemia* enriched herbal diet containing *Andrographis paniculata*, *Eclipta erecta*, *Hygrophila spinosa*, *Ocimum sacnctum*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Phyllanthus niruri*, *Picrorhiza kurooa*, *Psoralea corylifolia*, *Solanum trilobatum*, *Tinospora cordifoliaare*, *Withania somnifera* and *Zingber officinale* for producing quality larvae in *Penaeus monodon*. Diab *et al.*, (2002) evaluated the impacts of *Nigella sativa* L (black seeds; baraka), *Allium sativum* (garlic) and Biogen as feed additives on growth performance and immunostimulants of *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. Richter *et al.*, (2003) studied the nutritional quality of moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) leaves as an alternative protein source for Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. Skidmore-Roth (2003) mentioned that *Acalypha indica*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Chrysopogon zizanioides*, *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Hordeum vulgare*, *Medicago sativa*, *Senna auriculata*, *Sorghum bicolor* and *Urtica dioica* are some of the most useful medicinal herbs that can be used as natural supplements.

Khattab *et al.*, (2004) studied the physiological changes and growth performance of the Nile tilapia *Oerochromis niloticus* after feeding with Biogen as growth promoter. Shalaby *et al.* (2004) observed the response of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, fingerlings to diets supplemented with different levels of fenugreek seeds. Chitmanat *et al.*, (2005) used the crude extracts of *Allium sativum* and *Terminalia catappa* plants to eliminate *Trichodina* sp. in *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. Micol *et al.* (2005) observed that olive leaf extract exhibits antiviral activity

against viral haemorrhagic *Septicaemia rhabdovirus*. Dongmeza *et al.*, (2006) observed the beneficial effects of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) leaves extracts on growth and feed nutrient assimilation in Nile tilapia. Shalaby *et al.*, (2006) reported that dietary Garlic (*Allium sativum*) improve the growth performance, physiological parameters and survival of *Oreochromis niloticus*. Turan (2006) observed the improvement of growth performance in *Oreochromis aureus* by supplementation of red clover *Trifolium pratense* in diets. Yin *et al.* (2006) noticed the effectively of two Chinese herbs *Astragalus radix* and *Scutellaria radix* on non-specific immune response of tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*.

John *et al.*, (2007) studied the immunostimulant effects of *Allium sativum*, *Echinacea purpurea* and *Nigella sativum* as feed additives on the survival and growth performance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* and their response to artificial infection. Ardo *et al.*, (2008) showed that chinese herbs *Astragalus membranaceus* and *Lonicera japonica* with boron enhance the non-specific immune response of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and resistance against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Ashraf and Goda (2008) mentioned that dietary Ginseng herb *Eleutherococcus senticosus* supplementation improved growth, feed utilization, and hematological indices of Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. Goda (2008) observed that dietary ginseng herb (Ginsana® G115) supplementation improved growth, feed utilization, and hematological indices of *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. Pachanawan *et al.* (2008) observed the potential of *Psidium guajava* supplemented fish diets in controlling *Aeromonas hydrophila* infection in tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. Thy *et al.*, (2008) studied the effects of water spinach and duckweed on fish growth performance in poly-culture ponds. Won *et al.* (2008) found that residum extract of Siberian ginseng *Eleutherococcus senticosus* increased non-specific immunity in olive flounder *Paralichthys olivaceu*.

Yin *et al.*, (2008) reported that *Astragalus radix*, *Lonicera japonica* and *Ganoderma lucidum* enhanced the non-specific immune response of tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, and protection against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Yuan *et al.* (2008) found the appreciable effects of *Astragalus membranaceus* extracts on the expression of immune response genes in head kidney, gill and spleen of the common carp, *Cyprinus carpio*. Zakes

et al. (2008) studied the effects of *Lonicera japonica* on the growth performance and body composition of juvenile pike perch (*Sander lucioperca*). Ergun *et al.*, (2009) proved the influence of *Ulva lactuca* meal on growth, feed utilization, and body composition of juvenile Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* at two levels of dietary lipid. Immanuel *et al.*, (2009) noticed that the extracts of *Aegle marmelos*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Withania somnifera* and *Zingiber officinale* improved the growth, immune activity and survival of tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus*. Jeney *et al.* (2009) mentioned that addition of different single herbal extracts of the herbs *Artemisia capillaries*, *Cnidium officinale*, *Crataegi fructus*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Isatis tinctoria*, *Massa medicate* and *Polygonum multiflorum* promoted the growth and enhanced some non-specific immunity indicators of fish. Omoregie *et al.*, (2009) studied effect of varying levels of sweet potato *Ipomea batatas* peels on growth, feed utilization and some biochemical responses of the Cichlid *Oreochromis niloticus*.

Rattanachaikunsopon and Phumkhachorn (2009) observed the prophylactic effect of *Andrographis paniculata* extracts against *Streptococcus agalactiae* infection in Nile tilapia. Yin *et al.*, (2009) reported that Chinese herbs (*Astragalus radix* and *Ganoderma lucidum*) enhance immune response of carp, *Cyprinus carpio*, and protection against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Abdel-Tawwab *et al.*, (2010) showed that use of green tea, *Camellia sinensis* L., in practical diet improved growth performance and immune responses in Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila* infection. Citarasu (2010) noticed that Ricebran *Oryza sativa* improved the survival and reproductive performance in fish *Artemia parthenogenetica*. Kirubakaran *et al.*, (2010) Enhancement of non-specific immune responses and disease resistance on oral administration of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* seed extract in *Oreochromis mossambicus*. Sharma *et al.* (2010) observed the efficacy of *Withania somnifera* root as a feed additive on immunological parameters and disease resistance to *Aeromonas hydrophila* in *Labeo rohita* fingerlings. Zilberg *et al.*, (2010) used dried leaves of *Rosmarinus officinalis* as a treatment for streptococcosis in tilapia.

Ahmad and Abdel-Tawwab (2011) used caraway (*Carum carvi*) seed meal as a feed additive in fish diets to improve growth performance, feed utilization, and whole-body composition of Nile

tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.) fingerlings. Chakraborty and Hancz (2011) studied the application of phytochemicals as immunostimulant, antipathogenic and antistress agents in finfish culture. Coutteau *et al.* (2011) mentioned that extracts of *Allium tuberosum*, *Aniba rosaeodora*, *Capsicum annum longum*, *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, *Elettaria caramomum*, *Mentha piperita*, *Myristica flagrans*, *Piper nigrum*, *Salviaapiana* and *Syzygium aromaticum* improves the productivity and economics in aquaculture. Joseph *et al.* (2011) observed the influence of *Crossandra infundibuliformis*, *Hibiscus rosasinensis*, *Ixora coccinea* and *Rosa indica* flowers on the growth and colouration of orange sword tail Chicilidae fish *Xiphophorus hellerei*. Kaleeswaran *et al.*, (2011) observed improved growth response, feed conversion ratio and antiprotease activity in *Catla catla* (Ham.) fed on *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) mixed diet. Obaroh and Achionye-Nzeh (2011) studied the effects of crude extract of *Azadirachta indica* leaves at controlling prolific breeding in *Oreochromis niloticus*.

Arumugam *et al.* (2012) observed the effect of dietary *Nelumbo nucifera* in growth and haematology of *Cirrhinus mrigala* challenged with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Arenl *et al.*, (2012) observed that aqueous extract of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* decreases levels of blood glucose in induced hyperglycemic tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Benny *et al.* (2012) investigated the immunostimulatory behaviour of *Musa acuminata* peel extract in *Clarias batrachus*. Elkamel and Mosaad (2012) reported improved immunomodulation of Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, by *Nigella sativa* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Falaye *et al.* (2012) replaced the maize *Zea mays* using cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* hull meal in practical feeds of African catfish *Clarias gariepinus*. Jha *et al.* (2012) studied the effects of marigold flower *Beta vulgaris* and beetroot *Calendula officinalis* meals on growth performance, carcass composition, and total carotenoids of snow trout *Schizothorax richardsonii*. Lee and Gao (2012) review of the application of garlic, *Allium sativum*, in aquaculture. Park and Choi (2012) studied the effect of *Prunella vulgaris* and *Viscum album coloratum*, extract on innate immune response of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

Sivagurunathan *et al.*, (2012a) observed that effect of dietary *Nelumbo nucifera* (lotus) improved growth, immunity and haematology of *Cirrhinus mrigala* challenged with *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa. Sivagurunathan *et al.*, (2012b) observed the Immunostimulatory potential of dietary amla *Phyllanthus emblica* in growth and hematology of *Tilapia mossambicus* challenged with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Yılmaz and Ergün (2012a) noticed that dietary *Allium sativum* and *Zingiber officinale* oils on enriched the hematological and biochemical variables of sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax*. Yılmaz *et al.*, (2012b) showed that of *Cuminum cyminum* supplemented diets improve the growth and disease (*Streptococcus Iniae*) resistance of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). Zaki *et al.*, (2012) quoted that dietary *Capsicum frutescens*, *Eucalyptus citrodora* and *Matricaria recutit* promote growth performance, feed utilization and physiological parameters of mono sex Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

Ampofo-Yeboah (2013) studied the effect of *Moringa oleifera* and *Carica papaya* as phyto-genic feed additives on gonadal development in Mozambique tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). Emmanuelle *et al.*, (2013) observed the utility of vital wheat gluten in aquaculture feeds. Hwang *et al.*, (2013) observed that dietary green tea *Camellia sinensis* extract improves growth performance, body composition, and stress recovery in the juvenile black rockfish, *Sebastes schlegeli*. Madalla *et al.*, (2013) evaluated the effects of aqueous extracted *Moringa oleifera* leaf meal as a protein source for Nile tilapia juveniles. Mamman *et al.* (2013) studied the hematological indices of *Clarias griepinus* fingerlings fed diet containing graded levels of calabash *Lagenaria vulgaris* seed meal. Wu *et al.*, (2013) studied the effect of *Sophora flavescens* on non-specific immune response of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and disease resistance against *Streptococcus agalactiae*. Yılmaz *et al.*, (2013a) observed the enhancement of growth performance and pigmentation in red *Oreochromis mossambicus* associated with dietary intake of astaxanthin, paprika, or *Capsicum frutescens*. Yılmaz *et al.*, (2013b) reported that dietary supplementation of cumin *Cuminum cyminum* prevents streptococcal disease during first feeding of Mozambique tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus*.

Borkar *et al.* (2014) evaluated the impact of shatavari *Asparagus racemosus* and ashwagandha *Withania somnifera* on average body weight of freshwater fish *Channa punctatus*. Dotta *et al.*, (2014) observed the leukocyte phagocytosis and lysozyme activity in Nile tilapia fed supplemented diet with natural extracts of propolis and *Aloe*

barbadensis. El-Sayed *et al.*, (2014) studied the effects of dietary *Echinacea purpurea* as natural feed additives in comparison with antibiotic on growth performance and immune status of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Gaber *et al.*, (2014) observed the mentioned that dietary *Alternaria storini*, *Hippophae rhamnoides* *Phoenix dactylifera* and *Thymus vulgaris* improves the growth performance in Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. Ghosal and Chakraborty (2014) observed the effects of the aqueous leaf extract of *Basella alba* on sex reversal Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*. Gültepe *et al.*, (2014a) reported that dietary *Tribulus terrestris* extract supplementation improved growth, feed utilization, hematological, immunological and biochemical variables of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. Gültepe *et al.*, (2014b) studied the effects of *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Thymus vulgaris* and *Trigonella foenum graecum* on health status of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) challenged with *Streptococcus iniae*.

Hlophe and Moyo (2014) performed comparative study on the use of *Pennisetum clandestinum* and *Moringa oleifera* as protein sources in the diet of the herbivorous Tilapia rendalli. Karpagam and Krishnaveni (2014) noticed that *Coleus aromaticus*, *Moringa oleifera*, *Ocimum basilium*, *Sesbania grandiflora* and *Solanum verbascifolium* supplementation improved the growth performance of tilapia fish (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). Nath *et al.*, (2014) observed the Asian catfish fry (*Clarias batrachus*) reared with wheatgrass powder mixed formulated feed in plastic half drum. Tang *et al.*, (2014) proved that artificial feed supplemented with a Chinese herbal mixture (*Angelica*, Hawthorn, Honeysuckle and *Astragalus membranaceus*) enriched the immunity of *Oreochromis niloticus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Yilmaz and Ergün (2014) observed that dietary supplementation with allspice *Pimenta dioica* reduced the occurrence of streptococcal disease during first feeding of Mozambique tilapia fry. Yilmaz *et al.*, (2014) noticed progressive effects of *Tribulus terrestris* extract on the survival and histopathology of *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters, 1852) fry before and after *Streptococcus iniae* infection. Zahran *et al.*, (2014) studied the effects of dietary *Astragalus* polysaccharides on growth performance, immunological parameters, digestive enzymes and intestinal morphology of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

Acar *et al.*, (2015) performed the evaluation of the effects of essential oil extracted from sweet

orange peel (*Citrus sinensis*) on growth rate of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) and possible disease resistance against *Streptococcus iniae*. Adel *et al.* (2015) observed the effects of dietary peppermint *Mentha piperita* on growth performance, chemical body composition and hematological and immune parameters of fry Caspian white fish. Gabriel (2015a, b) observed that dietary *Aloe vera* supplementation improved the growth performance, some haemato-biochemical parameters, plasma lipid profile, antioxidant, hepatoprotective enzyme activities and disease resistance in GIFT-tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) after *Streptococcus iniae* challenge. Gurkan *et al.*, (2015) studied the influence of *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Thymus vulgaris* and *Trigonella foenum graecum* on the survival and histopathology of *Oreochromis mossambicus* before and after *Streptococcus iniae* infection. Nagarajan *et al.*, (2015) studied the properties and characteristics of nanocomposite films from tilapia skin gelatin incorporated with ethanolic extract from coconut husk. Yang *et al.*, (2015) studied the effects of *Ficus carica* polysaccharide on immune response and expression of some immune related genes in grass carp, *Ctenopharyngodon idella*. Yilmaz *et al.*, (2015) evaluated the effects of dietary allspice, *Pimenta dioica* powder on physiological responses of *Oreochromis mossambicus* under low pH stress. Baba *et al.*, (2016) evaluated of *Citrus limon* peels essential oil on growth performance, immune response of Mozambique tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus* challenged with *Edwardsiella tarda*.

Güllü *et al.*, (2016) observed the beneficial effects of Oral Allspice, *Pimenta dioica* powder supplementation on the hemato-immunological and serum biochemical responses of *Oreochromis mossambicus*. Kareem *et al.*, (2016) observed that dietary *Azadirachta indica*, *Cinnamomum camphora* and *Euphorbia hirta* extracts improved the growth and gonadal maturity of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and resistance during *Streptococcus agalactiae* infection. Labh and Shakya (2016) studied the effects of dietary lapsi (*Choerospondias axillaris*) on survival, growth and protein profile of common carp *Cyprinus carpio* fingerlings. Mo *et al.*, (2016) reported the enhanced growth and non-specific immunity of grass carp and Nile tilapia by incorporating Chinese herbs *Astragalus membranaceus* and *Lycium barbarum* into food waste based pellets. Quezada-Rodríguez and Fajer-Ávila (2016) studied the dietary effects of ulvan from *Ulva clathrata* on hematological-

immunological parameters and growth of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Gabriel *et al.*, (2017) noticed the sex-reversal effect of dietary *Aloe vera* (Liliaceae) on genetically improved farmed Nile tilapia fry. Kaur and Shah (2017) mentioned the efficacy of Vegetable Colour from Red Sandal *Pterocarpus santalinus* on acceptability, colour development and growth of Tilapia *Tilapia mossambica*. Makode (2017) studied the effects of dietary onion on growth performance in the fresh water fish *Clarias batrachus*. Mirela *et al.*, (2017) studied the effects of dietary supplementation with Sea-buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*) and Spirulina (*Spirulina platensis*) on the growth performance of some sturgeon hybrids. Makode *et al.*, (2018) studied the effects of dietary onion on behaviour of the fresh water fish *Channa punctatus*. Butle *et al.*, (2018) and Rodge *et al.*, (2018) studied the dietary garlic induced effects on behaviour responses, growth performance, feed utilization hematology and biochemistry of *Clarias batrachus*. Plaza *et al.* (2018) observed the effect of spirulina *Arthrospira platensis* supplementation on tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* growth and stress responsiveness under hypoxia.

Gabriel *et al.*, (2019) studied the effect of dietary *Aloe vera* on growth performance, feed utilization, hemato-biochemical parameters, and survival at low pH in African catfish *Clarias gariepinus*. Roghieh *et al.*, (2019) assessed the effects of *Coriandrum sativum* as feed additive on mucosal immune parameters, antioxidant defense and, immune-related genes expression in Zebrafish *Danio rerio*. Yilmaz (2019a) studied the effects of dietary blackberry syrup supplement on growth performance, antioxidant, and immunological responses, and resistance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* to *Plesiomonas shigelloides*. Yilmaz (2019b) observed the effects of dietary caffeic acid on antioxidant, immunological and liver gene expression responses, and resistance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* to *Aeromonas veronii*. Abdus *et al.* (2020a) conducted an experiment to produce hydroponic wheatgrass and feeding trials with stinging catfish, rohu and grass carp.

Abdus *et al.* (2020b) observed the growth response of juvenile rohu (*Labeo rohita*) to wheatgrass powder supplemented diet. Goswami *et al.*, (2020) observed the growth performance and digestive enzyme activities of rohu *Labeo rohita* fed diets containing macrophytes and almond oil-cake. Salam *et al.*, (2020) studied the growth response of

juvenile rohu (*Labeo rohita*) to wheatgrass powder supplemented diet. Shakil *et al.*, (2020) studied the dietary supplementation of wheatgrass powder to assess somatic response of juvenile grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*). The overall somatic performance of grass carp fed wheatgrass supplemented test diets was satisfactory compared to control diet without wheatgrass. Notably, fish survival was substantially improved. Pradhan *et al.*, (2021) observed the influence of fishmeal-replaced diet on nutrient digestibility, digestive enzyme activity, and whole-body fatty acid profile of Indian major carp, *Cirrhinus mrigala*. The feed conversion ratio value and feed formulation cost of the respective diets were reduced in a good amount.

Importance of herbal feed supplements in aquaculture

According to Shakya (2017), many factors such as density, water quality, feed quality and various environmental factors such as temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen content of water play important role in increasing the meat quality and production in aquaculture. Besides the above mentioned factors disease outbreak, environmental conditions like rain, excessive temperature, floods, landslides, entry of predatory fish in the culture ponds or reservoirs, algal bloom etc. are also the cause of decreased aquaculture product. These factors cause stress and underutilization of normal feed leading to low feed conversion ratio. The antibiotics and synthetic drugs used to control diseases could damage the organs like liver and affect growth of fishes under culture leading to decreased productivity. To increase the economically viable production by solving the above problems, a proper herbal feed supplementation is required to take care of overall health of fishes and withstand the environmental challenges without affecting the growth survivability.

Gaps in the existing knowledge and way forward

Constraints associated with the wide adoption of intensive aquaculture farming systems such as increased susceptibility to diseases and poor meat quality among others cannot be over-emphasized. And the consequent use of chemotherapeutic drugs to improve production appears to be more production-oriented, while ignoring the potential impacts these chemicals might have on the environment, humans, and animals. The findings of this review paper gives an impression that there are several medicinal herbs that indeed possess ability to enhance growth, feed

utilization, immune response (both innate and specific), antioxidation, hepatoprotective activity, resistance against disease, and control reproduction in tilapia culture. However, the pace of implementation of this innovation is slow, despite numerous advantages associated with it, as mentioned earlier.

Gabriel (2019) quoted that effective application of herbs in fresh water fish culture in general is limited in many ways. These limitations include lack of sufficient knowledge on effective herb based feed formulation, possible effects of such feed on fish physiological processes, meat quality and further consequences related to environment and consumers. In addition to these limitations, effects of herb based formulated feed in fish at different life stages like fries, fingerlings, juveniles, pre- adults and adults are also unknown.

Therefore, the need to research more and standardize every aspect around the use of herbal extracts in freshwater fish culture is overwhelming. Moreover, exploration and implementation of herbs in farmed fish culture in general has to be done in a sustainable manner, as adopting them in aquaculture may double the pressure already exerted by agricultural sectors and humans.

CONCLUSION

This review reveals that there are numerous medicinal plants with potential to enhance growth, several physiological parameters in farmed fish. However, the lack of sufficient knowledge on herbal extracts limits the cost-effective use of herb based formulated feed aquaculture. Therefore, more research is required to further validate herb based fish feed with their allied growth-promoting effects, immune-stimulating effects, nutrient enriching as well possible toxicity effects among farmed fish species. Conclusively, it will help to produce healthy fishes for human consumption.

REFERENCES

Abdel-Tawwab M, Ahmad M, Seden MEA, Sakr SFM, 2010. Use of green tea, *Camellia sinensis* L., in practical diet for growth and protection Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.), against *Aeromonas hydrophila* infection. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, **41**: 203–2013.

Abdus S, Shakil R, Rakib A, Noor M, 2020b. Growth response of juvenile rohu (*Labeo rohita*) to wheatgrass powder supplemented diet. *Res. Agri. Live. Fish.* **7**(3): 533-543

Abdus SM, Das SC, Noor AM, Sultana M, 2020a. *Development of hydroponic wheatgrass cultivation as supplementary feed production techniques for fish and*

poultry farming in Bangladesh. Pamphlet Published by Department of Aquaculture, Bangladesh Agriculture University, Mymensingh. 1-2 pp.

Acar Ü, Kesbic OS, Yilmaz S, Gültepe N, Türker A, 2015. Evaluation of the effects of essential oil extracted from sweet orange peel (*Citrus sinensis*) on growth rate of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) and possible disease resistance against *Streptococcus iniae*. *Aquaculture*, **43**(7): 282–286.

Adel M, Abedian-Amiri A, Zorriehzahra J, Nematollahi A, Esteban M, 2015. Effects of dietary peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) on growth performance, chemical body composition and hematological and immune parameters of fry Caspian white fish (*Rutilus frisii-kutum*). *Fish Shellfish Immunol.* **45**(2):841-847.

Ahmad MH, Abdel-Tawwab M, 2011. The use of caraway seed meal as a feed additive in fish diets: Growth performance, feed utilization, and whole-body composition of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.) fingerlings. *Aquaculture*, **31**(4): 110–114.

Ampofo-Yeboah A, 2013. *Effect of phytogenic feed additives on gonadal development in Mozambique tilapia (Oreochromis mossambicus).* (PhD thesis), University of Stellenbosch, South Africa. 168 pp.

Ardo L, Yin G, Xu P, Váradi L, Szigeti G, Jeney Z, Jeney G, 2008. Chinese herbs (*Astragalus membranaceus* and *Lonicera japonica*) and boron enhance the non-specific immune response of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and resistance against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Aquaculture*, **27**(5): 26–33.

Arenal A, Martín L, Castillo NM, de la Torre D, Torres U, González R, 2012. Aqueous extract of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* decreases levels of blood glucose in induced hyperglycemic tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, **5**(8): 634–637.

Arumugam S, Innocent B, Muthulakshmi S, 2012. Immunomodulatory effect of dietary *Nelumbo nucifera* (lotus) in growth and haematology of *Cirrhinus mrigala* challenged with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *J Appl Pharm Sci.*, **2**: 191-195.

Ashraf MA, Goda S, 2008. Effect of dietary Ginseng herb (Ginsana® G115) supplementation on growth, feed utilization, and hematological indices of Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.), fingerlings. *J World Aquac Soc*, **39**(2):205–214.

Baba E, Acar U, Ontas C, Kesbic OS, Yilmaz S, 2016. Evaluation of *Citrus limon* peels essential oil on growth performance, immune response of Mozambique tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus* challenged with *Edwardsiella tarda*. *Aquaculture*, **46**(5): 13–18.

Basha KA, Raman RP, Pradsad KP, Kumar K, Nilavan E, Kumar S, 2013. Effect of dietary supplemented andrographolide on growth, non-specific immune parameters and resistance against *Aeromonas hydrophila* in *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton). *Fish and Shellfish Immunology*, **35**: 1433–1441.

- Benny P, Viswanathan G, Thomas S, Nair A, 2012.** Investigation of immunostimulatory behaviour of *Musa acuminata* peel extract in *Clarias batrachus*. *IIOAB Journal*. **1**(2): 39-43.
- Borkar SB, Rathod SH, Kulkarni KM, Tantarapale VT, 2014.** Impact of shatavari and ashwagandha on average body weight of freshwater fish *Channa punctatus*. *Journal of Global Biosciences*. **3**(2): 582-585.
- Butle SS, Thakare VG, Joshi PS, 2018.** Study of dietary garlic induced effects on behaviour responses, growth performance and feed utilization in *Clarias batrachus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Bioscience Discovery*, **9**(3): 403-408
- Chakraborty SB, Hancz C, 2011.** Application of phytochemicals as immunostimulant, antipathogenic and antistress agents in finfish culture. *Reviews in Aquaculture*. **3**(3): 103-119.
- Chitmanat C, Tongdonmuan K, Nunsong W, 2005.** The use of crude extracts from traditional medicinal plants to eliminate *Trichodina* sp. in tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings. *Songkl. J. Sci, Technol.*, **27**(1): 359– 364.
- Citarasu T, 2010.** Herbal biomedicines: a new opportunity for aquaculture industry. *Aquacult Int*. **18**: 403–414.
- Citarasu T, Babu MM, Punitha SMJ, Venketa RK, Marian MP, 2001.** Control of pathogenic bacteria using herbal biomedical products in the larva culture system of *Penaeus monodon*. In *Proceeding of International Conference on Advanced Technologies in Fisheries and Marine Sciences*; Tirunelveli, India. 104 pp.
- Citarasu T, Sekar RR, Babu MM, Marian MP, 2002.** Developing *Artemia* enriched herbal diet for producing quality larvae in *Penaeus monodon* (Fabricius). *Asian Fish Sci*. **15**:21–32.
- Coutteau P, Ceulemans S, Alexander H, 2011.** Botanical extracts improve productivity and economics in aquaculture. *Nutriad Int., Belgium*. **11**: 1-8
- Diab AS, El-Nagar GO, Abd-El-Hady YM, 2002.** Evaluation of *Nigella sativa* L (black seeds; baraka), *Allium sativum* (garlic) and BIOGEN as feed additives on growth performance and immunostimulants of *O. niloticus* fingerlings. *Suez Canal Vet Me. J*. **2**:745–775.
- Dongmeza E, Siddhuraju P, Francis G, Becker K, 2006.** Effects of dehydrated methanol extracts of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) leaves and three of its fractions on growth and feed nutrient assimilation in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus* L.). *Aquacult.*, **26**(1): 407–422.
- Dotta G, de Andrade JIA, Gonçalves ELT, Brum A, Mattos JJ, Maraschin M, Martins ML, 2014.** Leukocyte phagocytosis and lysozyme activity in Nile tilapia fed supplemented diet with natural extracts of propolis and *Aloe barbadensis*. *Fish & Shellfish Immunology*, **39**(2): 280–284.
- Elkamel,AA, Mosaad GM, 2012.** Immunomodulation of Nile Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, by *Nigella sativa* and *Bacillus subtilis*. *Journal of Aquaculture & Research Development*, **3**(6):1-5.
- El-Sayed SAA, El-Galil SYA, Rashied NA, 2014.** Effects of Some herbal plants as natural feed additives in comparison with antibiotic on growth performance and immune status of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Urp*, **4**: 22–30.
- Emmanuelle A, Aurélien F, Anne A, Respondek F, 2013.** Use of vital wheat gluten in aquaculture feeds. *Aqua. Bios*. **9**(21): 1-13.
- Ergun S, Soyuturk M, Guroy B, Guroy D, Merrifield D, 2009.** Influence of Ulva meal on growth, feed utilization, and body composition of juvenile Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) at two levels of dietary lipid. *Aquacult Int*. **17**: 355-361.
- Falaye AE, Omoike A, Olasebikan OB, 2012.** Replacement of maize (*Zea mays*) using cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) hull meal in practical feeds of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fry. *International Journal of Plant, Animal and Environmental Sciences*. **2**(3):178-182.
- FAO, 2016.** *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization. **160**: 1-194.
- Gaber MM, Labib EH, Omar EA, Zaki MA, Nour AM, 2014.** Effect of partially replacing corn meal by wet date on growth performance in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings, diets supplemented with digestarom. *Journal of Geoscience and Environment Protection*. **2**:60-67.
- Gabriel NN, 2019.** Review on the progress in the role of herbal extracts in tilapia culture, *Cogent Food and Agriculture*, **5**(1):1-21.
- Gabriel NN, Qiang J, He J, Ma XY, Kpundeh MD, Xu P, 2015a.** Dietary *Aloe vera* supplementation on growth performance, some haemato-biochemical parameters and disease resistance against *Streptococcus iniae* in tilapia (GIFT). *Fish and Shellfish Immunology*, **44**: 504–514.
- Gabriel NN, Qiang J, Ma XY, He J, Xu P, Liu K, 2015b.** Dietary *Aloe vera* improves plasma lipid profile, antioxidant, and hepatoprotective enzyme activities in GIFT-tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) after *Streptococcus iniae* challenge. *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, **41**(5):1321–1332.
- Gabriel, N. N., Qiang, J., Ma, X. Y., He, J., Xu, P., Omoregie, E. (2017). Sex-reversal effect of dietary *Aloe vera* (Liliaceae) on genetically improved farmed Nile tilapia fry. *North American Journal of Aquaculture*, **79**(1), 100–105.
- Gabriel NN, Wilhelm MR, Shimoosshil K, 2019.** Effect of dietary *Aloe vera* polysaccharides supplementation on growth performance, feed utilization, hemato-biochemical parameters, and survival at low pH in African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) fingerlings. *Int. Aquatic Research*, **11**: 57–72.
- Ghosal I, Chakraborty BS, 2014.** Effects of the aqueous leaf extract of *Basella alba* on sex reversal Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* L. *Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*, **9**: 162–164.

- Goda AMAS, 2008.** Effect of dietary ginseng herb (Ginsana ® G115) supplementation on growth, feed utilization, and hematological indices of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* (L.), fingerlings. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, **39**(2), 205–214.
- Goswami RK, Shrivastav AK, Sharma JG, Tocher DR, Chakrabarti C, 2020.** Growth and digestive enzyme activities of rohu *Labeo rohita* fed diets containing macrophytes and almond oil-cake. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, **26**(3): 1-8.
- Güllü, K., Acar, Ü., Kesbiç, O. S., Yılmaz, S., Ağdamar, S., Ergün, S., Türker, A. (2016).** Beneficial effects of Oral Allspice, *Pimenta dioica* powder supplementation on the hemato-immunological and serum biochemical responses of *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Aquaculture Research*, **47**(9):2697–2704.
- Gültepe N, Acar U, Kesbi OS, Yılmaz S, Yıldırım O, Turker A, 2014a.** Effects of dietary *Tribulus terrestris* extract supplementation on growth, feed utilization, hematological, immunological and biochemical variables of Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*. *Israeli Journal of Aquaculture-Bamidgeh*, **66**:1–8.
- Gültepe N, Bilen S, Yılmaz S, Güroy D, Aydın S, 2014b.** Effects of herbs and spice on health status of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) challenged with *Streptococcus iniae*. *Acta Veterinaria Brno*, **83**: 129–135.
- Gurkan M, Yilmaz S, Kaya H, Ergun S, Alkan S, 2015.** Influence of three spice powders on the survival and histopathology of *Oreochromis mossambicus* before and after *Streptococcus iniae* infection. *The Marine Science and Technology Bulletin*, **4**(1): 1-5.
- Hlophe SN, Moyo NAG, 2014.** A comparative study on the use of *Pennisetum clandestinum* and *Moringa oleifera* as protein sources in the diet of the herbivorous Tilapia rendalli. *Aquaculture International*, **22**(4):1245–1262.
- Hwang JH, Lee, SW, Rha SJ, Yoon HS, Park ES, Han KH, Kim SJ, 2013.** Dietary green tea extract improves growth performance, body rock composition, and stress recovery in the juvenile black rockfish, *Sebastes schlegeli*. *Aquacult Internat.*, **21**: 525-538.
- Immanuel G, Uma RP, Iyapparaj P, Citarasu T, Punitha PSM, Michael BM, Palavesam A, 2009.** Dietary medicinal plant extracts improve growth, immune activity and survival of tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Journal of Fish Biology*, **74**(7): 1462–1475.
- Jeney G, Yin G, Ardo L, Jeney Z, 2009.** The use of immunostimulating herbs in fish. An overview of research. *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, **35**:669-676.
- Jha GN, Sarma D, Qureshi TA, Akhtar MS, 2012.** Effect of marigold flower and beetroot meals on growth performance, carcass composition, and total carotenoids of snow trout (*Schizothorax richardsonii*). *The Israeli Journal of Aquaculture*, **12**:1-5.
- Ji SC, Jeong GS, Im GS, Lee SW, Yoo JH, Takii K, 2007.** Dietary medicinal herbs improve growth performance, fatty acid utilization, and stress recovery of Japanese flounder. *Fisheries Science*, **73**(1): 70–76.
- Jittinandana S, Kenney P, Slider S, Masik P, Bebak-Williams J, Hankins J, A. (2003).** Effect of fish attributes and handling stress. *Journal of Food Science*, **68**(1): 57-63.
- John G, Mesalhy S, Rezk M, El-Naggar G, Fathi M, 2007.** Effect of some immunostimulants as feed additives on the survival and growth performance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* and their response to artificial infection. *Egypt J Aquat Biol Fish*. **11**(3): 1299 - 1308.
- Joseph B, Sujath S, Shalin J, Palavesam A, 2011.** Influence of Four ornamental flowers on the growth and colouration of orange sword tail Chicilidae fish (*Xiphophorus hellerei*, Heckel, 1940). *International J. of Biological and Medical Research*, **2**(3):621-626.
- Kaleeswaran B, Ilavenil S, Ravikumar S 2011.** Growth Response, Feed Conversion Ratio and Antiprotease Activity of *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Mixed Diet in *Catla catla* (Ham.). *J Anim Vet Adv.*, **10**(4): 511-517.
- Kareem ZH, Abdelhadi YM, Christianus A, Karim M, Romano N, 2016.** Effects of some dietary crude plant extracts on the growth and gonadal maturity of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and their resistance to *Streptococcus agalactiae* infection. *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, **42**(2): 757–769.
- Karpagam B, Krishnaveni N, 2014.** Effect of Supplementation of Selected Plant Leaves as Growth Promoters of Tilapia Fish (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). *Res J Recent Sci.*, **3**:120-123.
- Kaur R, Shah T, 2017.** A review on role of plant waste products on fish growth, health and production. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, **5**(3): 583-589.
- Khattab YA, Shalaby AMS, Sharaf SM, EL-Marakby HI, Rizhalla EH, 2004.** The physiological changes and growth performance of the Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus* after feeding with Biogen® as growth promoter. *Egypt J. Aquatic Biol. Fish.*, **8**: 145-158.
- Kirubakaran CJW, Alexander CP, Michael RD, 2010.** Enhancement of non-specific immune responses and disease resistance on oral administration of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* seed extract in *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters). *Aquaculture Research*, **41**(11): 1630–1639.
- Labh SN, Shakya SR, 2016.** Effects of dietary lapsi (*Choerospondias axillaris* Roxb.) on survival, growth and protein profile of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L) fingerlings. *Int j Zool Stud*. **1**(5): 36-415.
- Lee JY, Gao Y, 2012.** Review of the application of garlic, *Allium sativum*, in aquaculture. *J World Aquac Soc*, **43**: 447-458.
- Madalla N, Agbo NW, Jauncey K, 2013.** Evaluation of aqueous extracted moringa leaf meal as a protein source for Nile tilapia juveniles. *Tajas*, **12**(1):53–64.
- Mahdavi M, Hajimoradloo A, Ghorbani R, 2013.** Effect of *Aloe vera* extract on growth parameters of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *World Journal of Medical Sciences*, **9**(1): 55–60.

- Makode PM, 2017.** Effects of dietary onion on growth performance in the fresh water fish *Clarias batrachus* (Linn.). *Bioscience Discovery*, **8**(2):241-243.
- Makode P, Pandharikar S, Joshi P, Gulhane R, 2018.** Effects of dietary onion on behaviour of the fresh water fish *Channa punctatus* (Bloch, 1793). *ICRTST*: 70-72.
- Mamman T, Ipinjolu J, Magawata I, 2013.** Hematological indices of *Clarias griepinus* (Burchell, 1882) fingerlings fed diet containing graded levels of calabash (*Lagenaria vulgaris*) seed meal. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare*. **3**:100-104.
- Mckenzie DJ, Höglund E, Dupont-Prinet A, Larsen BK, Skov PV, Pedersen PB, Jokumsen A, 2012.** Effects of stocking density and sustained aerobic exercise on growth, energetics and welfare of rainbow trout. *Aquaculture*, **34**(1):216-222.
- Micol V, Caturla N, Perez-Fons L, Mas V, Perez L, Estepa A, 2005.** The olive leaf extract exhibits antiviral activity against viral haemorrhagic septicaemia rhabdovirus (VHSV). *Antiviral Research*. **66**(2-3):129-136.
- Mirela C, Angelica D, Victor C, Oana-Georgiana V, Lorena D, Raluca-Cristina A, 2017.** The effect of dietary supplementation with Sea-buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*) and Spirulina (*Spirulina platensis*) on the growth performance of some sturgeon hybrids. *AACL Bioflux*, **10**(5): 1157-1164.
- Mo WY, Lun CHI, Choi WM, Man YB, Wong MH, 2016.** Enhancing growth and non-specific immunity of grass carp and Nile tilapia by incorporating Chinese herbs (*Astragalus membranaceus* and *Lycium barbarum*) into food waste based pellets. *Environmental Pollution*, **21**(9):475-482.
- Nagarajan M, Benjakul S, Prodpran T, Songtipya P, 2015.** Properties and characteristics of nanocomposite films from tilapia skin gelatin incorporated with ethanolic extract from coconut husk. *The Journal of Food Science and Technology*, **52**: 7669-7682.
- Nath TD, Shaharior H, Salam MA, 2014.** Asian catfish fry (*Clarias batrachus*) rearing with wheatgrass powder mixed formulated feed in plastic half drum *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies* 2014; **1**(5): 162-168.
- Obaroh IO, Achionye-Nzeh GC, 2011.** Effects of Crude Extract of *Azadirachta indica* Leaves at Controlling Prolific Breeding in *Oreochromis niloticus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Asian Journal of Agricultural Research*, **5**: 277-282.
- Olusola SE, Emikpe BO, Olaiya FE, 2013.** The potentials of medicinal plant extracts as bio-antimicrobials in aquaculture. *International Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*, **3**(3):404-412.
- Omoriegbe E, 2001.** Utilization and nutrient digestibility of mango seeds and palm Kernel meal by juvenile *Labeo senegalensis* (Antheriniformes: Cyprinidae). *Aquaculture Research*. **32**:681-687.
- Omoriegbe E, Igoche L, Ojobe TO, Absalom KV, Onusiriukam BC, 2009.** Effect of varying levels of sweet potato (*Ipomea batatas*) peels on growth, feed utilization and some biochemical responses of the Cichlid (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *African Journal of Food Agri., Nutrition and Development*, **9**(2):1-7.
- Pachanawan A, Phumkhachorn P, Rattanachaikunsopon P, 2008.** Potential of *Psidium guajava* supplemented fish diets in controlling *Aeromonas hydrophila* infection in tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, **10**(6):419-424.
- Park KH Choi SH, 2012.** The effect of mistletoe, *Viscum album coloratum*, extract on innate immune response of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Fish & Shellfish Immunology*, **32**: 1016-1021.
- Plaza I, García JL, Villarroel M, 2018.** Effect of spirulina (*Arthrospira platensis*) supplementation on tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) growth and stress responsiveness under hypoxia. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, **16**(1):1-8.
- Pradhan C, Shiba SG, Satyandra NM, Khiroda CN, 2021.** Influence of fishmeal-replaced diet on nutrient digestibility, digestive enzyme activity, and whole-body fatty acid profile of Indian major carp, *Cirrhinus mrigala*. *The Journal of Basic and Applied Zoology*, **82**:2-10.
- Quezada-Rodríguez DRP, Fajer-Ávila EJ, 2016.** The dietary effect of ulvan from *Ulva clathrata* on hematological-immunological parameters and growth of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Journal of Applied Phycology*, **16**:1-9.
- Rattanachaikunsopon P, Phumkhachorn P, 2009.** Prophylactic effect of *Andrographis paniculata* extracts against *Streptococcus agalactiae* infection in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, **10**(7):579-582.
- Reverter M, Bontemps N, Lecchini D, Banaigs B, Sasal P, 2014.** Use of plant extracts in fish aquaculture as an alternative to chemotherapy: Current status and future perspectives. *Aquaculture*, **43**(3): 50-61.
- Richter N, Siddhuraju P, Becker K, 2003.** Evaluation of nutritional quality of moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) leaves as an alternative protein source for Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus* L.). *Aquacult.*, **217**(1-4): 599-611.
- Rodge SG, Thakare VG, Joshi PS, 2018.** Study of dietary garlic induced effects on hematology and biochemistry of *Clarias batrachus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Bioscience Discovery*, **9**(3): 411-415.
- Roghieh S, Seyed H, Maryam D, Masoud S, Mina R, 2019.** The effects of *Coriandrum sativum* L. as feed additive on mucosal immune parameters, antioxidant defence and immune-related genes expression in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Agri.Sci.*, **19**:1-8.
- Salam MA, Rana KMS, Ahmed MR, Noor AM, 2020.** Growth response of juvenile rohu (*Labeo rohita*) to wheatgrass powder supplemented diet. *Res. Agric. Livest. Fish.*, **7**(3): 533-543.
- Dietary supplementation of wheatgrass powder to assess somatic response of juvenile grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*). *Asian J. Med. Biol. Res.*(3): 482-490
- Shakya SR, 2017.** Effect of Herbs and Herbal Products Feed Supplements on Growth Resistance (Report of a Joint FAO/OIE/WHO Expert Consultation on Antimicrobial Use in Aquaculture and Antimicrobial Resistance). Seoul, Republic of Korea, 13-16.

- Shakil R, Salam MA, Rakib AM, Minan AN, 2020.** . 6in Fishes: A Review. *Nepal Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(1): 58-63.
- Shalaby SMM, 2004.** Response of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, fingerlings to diets supplemented with different levels of fenugreek seeds (Hulba). *J Agric Mansoura Univ.* 29:2231–2242.
- Shalaby AM, Khattab YA, Abdel Rahman AM, 2006.** Effects of Garlic (*Allium sativum*) and chlor- amphenicol on growth performance, physiological parameters and survival of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *J. Venom. Anim. Tox. Incl. Trop. Dis.*, 12(2):172–201.
- Sharma A, Deo AD, Riteshkumar ST, Chanu TI, Das A, 2010.** Effect of *Withania somnifera* (L Dunal) root as a feed additive on immunological parameters and disease resistance to *Aeromonas hydrophila* in *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton) fingerlings. *Fish and Shellfish Immunology*. 29:508-512.
- Sivagurunahan A, Xavier B, Gurusaraswathi S, Mariappan A, 2012.** Immunostimulatory potential of dietary amla *Phyllanthus emblica* in growth and hematology of *Tilapia mossambicus* challenged with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy*. 3(7): 165-168.
- Sivagurunathan A, Innocent BX, Muthulakshmi S, 2010.** Immunomodulatory effect of dietary *Nelumbo nucifera* (lotus) in growth and haematology of *Cirrhinus mrigala* challenged with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *J Appl Pharm Sci.* 2: 191-195.
- Skidmore-Roth L, 2003.** *Handbook of Herbs and Natural Supplements*. 2nd Edn. St. Louis: Mosby. 265 pp.
- Tang J, Cai J, Liu R, Wang J, Lu Y, Wu Z, Jian J, 2014.** Immunostimulatory effects of artificial feed supplemented with a Chinese herbal mixture on *Oreochromis niloticus* against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Fish, Shellfish Immunology*, 39(2): 401–406.
- Thy S, Khieu B, Vanvuth T, Thomas RP, 2008.** Effect of water spinach and duckweed on fish growth performance in poly-culture ponds. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 20(1): 1-6.
- Turan F, 2006.** Improvement of growth performance in tilapia (*Oreochromis aureus* Linnaeus) by supplementation of red clover *Trifolium pratense* in diets. *Israeli J. Aquacult.*, 58: 34-38.
- Waite R, Beveridge M, Brummett R, Castine S, Chaiyawannakarn N, Kaushik S, Phillips M, 2014.** Improving productivity and environmental performance of aquaculture. *Creating a Sustainable Food Future*, 6:1–60.
- Won KM, Kim PK, Lee SH, Park SI, 2008.** Effect of the residum extract of Siberian ginseng *Eleutherococcus senticosus* on non-specific immunity in olive flounder *Paralichthys olivaceus*. *Fisheries Science*. 74:635- 641.
- World Health Organization (WHO), 2006.** *Antimicrobial use in aquaculture and antimicrobial*
- Wu Y, Gong Q, Fang H, Liang W, Chen M, He R, 2013.** Effect of *Sophora flavescens* on non-specific immune response of tilapia (GIFT *Oreochromis niloticus*) and disease resistance against *Streptococcus agalactiae*. *Fish Shellfish Immunology*, 34(1): 220–227.
- Yang X, Guo JL, Ye JY, Zhang YX, Wang W, 2015.** The effects of *Ficus carica* polysaccharide on immune response and expression of some immune- related genes in grass carp, *Ctenopharyngodon idella*. *Fish & Shellfish Immunology*, 42(1): 132–137.
- Yilmaz S, 2019a.** Effects of dietary blackberry syrup supplement on growth performance, antioxidant, and immunological responses, and resistance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* to *Plesiomonas shigelloides*. *Fish & Shellfish Immunology*, 84: 1125–1133.
- Yilmaz S, 2019b.** Effects of dietary caffeic acid supplement on antioxidant, immunological and liver gene expression responses, and resistance of Nile tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus* to *Aeromonas veronii*. *Fish & Shellfish Immunology*, 86: 384–392.
- Yilmaz S, Acar Ü, Kesbiç OS, Gültepe N, Ergün S, 2015.** Effects of dietary allspice, *Pimenta dioica* powder on physiological responses of *Oreochromis mossambicus* under low pH stress. *SpringerPlus*, 4(1), 71-79.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, 2012.** Effects of garlic and ginger oils on hematological and biochemical variables of sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax*. *Journal of Aquatic Animal Health*, 24(4): 219–224.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, 2014.** Dietary supplementation with allspice *Pimenta dioica* reduces the occurrence of streptococcal disease during first feeding of Mozambique tilapia fry. *Journal of Aquatic Animal Health*, 26(3): 144–148.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, 2018.** Trans-cinnamic acid application for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*): Effects on haematological, serum biochemical, non-specific immune and head kidney gene expres- sion responses. *Fish Shellfish Immunology*, 78: 140–157.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, Kaya H, Gürkan M, 2014.** Influence of *Tribulus terrestris* extract on the survival and histopathology of *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters, 1852) fry before and after *Streptococcus iniae* infection. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology*, 30(5): 994–1000.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, Soytaş N, 2013a.** Enhancement of growth performance and pigmentation in red *Oreochromis mossambicus* associated with dietary intake of astaxanthin, paprika, or capsicum. *Israeli Journal of Aquaculture-Bamidgeh*, 65:1-5.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, Soytaş N, 2013b.** Dietary supplementation of cumin *Cuminum cyminum* preventing strepto- coccal disease during first feeding of Mozambique tilapia *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Journal of Bioscience and Biotechnology Discovery*, 2(2): 117–124.
- Yilmaz S, Ergün S, Türk N, 2012.** Effects of cumin supplemented diets on growth and disease (*Streptococcus Iniae*) resistance of tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*). *Isr. Israeli Journal of Aquaculture-Bamidgeh*, 64:1–5.

- Yin G, Jeney G, Racz T, Xu P, Jun X, Jeney Z, 2006.** Effect of two Chinese herbs (*Astragalus radix* and *Scutellaria radix*) on non-specific immune response of tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Aquaculture*, **25**(3):39-47.
- Yin G, Ardó L, Jeney Z, Xu P, Jeney G, 2008.** Chinese herbs (*Lonicera japonica* and *Ganoderma lucidum*) enhance non-specific immune response of tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*, and protection against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Disease in Asian Aquaculture*, **6**:269–282.
- Yin G, Ardo L, Thompson KD, Adams A, Jeney Z, Jeney G, 2009.** Chinese herbs (*Astragalus radix* and *Ganoderma lucidum*) enhance immune response of carp, *Cyprinus carpio*, and protection against *Aeromonas hydrophila*. *Fish Shellfish Immunology*, **26**(1): 140–145.
- Yuan C, Pan X, Gong Y, Xia A, Wu G, Tang J, 2008.** Effects of *Astragalus* polysaccharides (APS) on the expression of immune response genes in head kidney, gill and spleen of the common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* L. *International Immunopharma.*; **8**:51-58.
- Zahran E, Risha E, Abdelhamid F, Allah H, 2014.** Effects of dietary *Astragalus* polysaccharides (APS) on growth performance, immunological parameters, digestive enzymes, and intestinal morphology of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Fish Shellfish Immunology*, **38**(1): 149–157.
- Zakes Z, Kowalska A, Demska-Zakes K, Jeney G, Jeney Z, 2008.** Effect of two medicinal herbs (*Astragalus radix* and *Lonicera japonica*) on the growth performance and body composition of juvenile pike perch (*Sander lucioperca*). *Aquacult.* **39**:1149-1160.
- Zaki MA, Labib EM, Nour AM, Tonsy HD, Mahmoud SH, 2012.** Effect some medicinal plants diets on mono sex Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), growth performance, feed utilization and physiological parameters. *APCBEE Procedia*, **4**:220–227.
- Zanuzzo FS, Urbinati EC, Rise ML, Hall JR, Nash GW, Gamperl AK, 2015.** *Aeromonas salmonicida* induced immune gene expression in *aloe vera* fed steelhead trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Walbaum). *Aquaculture*, **43**(5): 1-9.
- Zhang P, Zhang X, Li J, Gao T, 2010.** Effect of refeeding on the growth and digestive enzyme activities of *Fenneropenaeus chinensis* juveniles exposed to different periods of food deprivation. *Aquaculture International*, **18**(6): 1191–1203.
- Zilberg D, Tal A, Froyman N, Abutbul S, Dudai N, Golan-Goldhirsh A, 2010.** Dried leaves of *Rosmarinus officinalis* as a treatment for streptococcosis in tilapia. *Journal of Fish Diseases*, **33**(4): 361–369.

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